

Environmental Perspectives on Wetland Degradation in Itu LGA, Nigeria.

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Abstract

This study examines wetland degradation in Itu Local Government Area using remote sensing and ground-truthing techniques. Land use changes between 1992 and 2022 were analyzed using Landsat satellite imagery. Results indicated minor reduction (0.696%) in water bodies, with an annual change rate of 0.209%, substantial wetland loss (39.877%), yearly change rate of 11.963% due to agriculture and urbanization. Followed land reduction (9.836%), annual change rate of 2.951%, cultivated land expansion (18.149%), yearly change rate of 5.445% and a significant built-up area growth (31.442%), annual change rate of 9.432%. Environmental implications of wetland degradation were found to include biodiversity loss, disrupted ecosystem services, hydrological shifts, reduced carbon sequestration, climate feedbacks, erosion impact, and cultural repercussions. This study underscores the need for holistic conservation efforts to mitigate the far-reaching consequences of wetland degradation.

Keywords: Wetlands, Degradation, and sustainability

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1) Introduction

Wetlands are transitional ecosystems where terrestrial areas interface with bodies of water. Essentially, wetlands encompass regions of land submerged under varying water depths (Ekong and Akpan, 2014). These areas are characterized by their flat, relatively shallow terrain, often situated in the downstream areas of expansive river watersheds in proximity to coastlines. Predominantly low-lying, these wetlands include floodplains that experience periodic inundation from runoff and groundwater flow originating from higher elevated slopes. Their significance stems from their capacity to host a diverse array of ecological functions, which subsequently yield a broad spectrum of biological assets (Gren *et al.*, 1994).

Despite their unique position in terms of environmental and economic roles, wetlands bear a noteworthy responsibility in catering to global societies by providing economic opportunities at modest levels of productivity and specific skills for marginalized communities, as they are actively utilized by various stakeholders (Abraham, 2004). The extent

of their exploitation has been so considerable that numerous regions have incurred irreparable losses (Ekong and Akpan, 2014). Ramsar (2014) documented that approximately 75 percent of the Earth's land has undergone degradation, with wetlands suffering the most, as 87 percent of them have been lost worldwide over the past three centuries. This phenomenon has eroded the quality of life for 3.2 billion individuals, as wetlands have experienced desertification, pollution, deforestation, or conversion for agricultural purposes. Consequently, this has propelled species extinction and other associated predicaments. The decline of wetlands can be attributed directly to factors like alterations in physical conditions such as hydrology and sedimentation, resource extraction encompassing water usage and fishing, the introduction of eutrophication, pollution, and invasive species, as well as structural modifications such as wetland drainage and conversion for alternative uses. Indirect drivers encompass the provisioning of water, energy, food, and fiber, infrastructure development, tourism, and recreational activities (Ramsar, 2014). These drivers are intertwined and profoundly influenced by both governance practices and the adverse effects of climate change.

Wetlands represent a valuable natural resource that delivers ecosystem benefits at both local and regional scales. Despite

their dispersed nature, their distinctive features contribute to global biogeochemical and hydrological cycles. Unfortunately, there is an ongoing decline in both the quantity and quality of wetland areas worldwide. In various countries, a significant portion, ranging from 30% to 90%, of the world's wetlands has already been lost or substantially altered. This loss and degradation of wetlands result in the unavailability of their crucial ecosystem benefits to communities (Verma and Prakash, 2023). Wetland degradation encompasses a range of processes that erode the health, functionality, and vitality of wetland ecosystems. This degradation is primarily driven by human activities, including urbanization, agriculture, industrialization, infrastructure development, and improper waste disposal. As these activities encroach upon wetlands, their delicate balance is disrupted, leading to irreversible changes in hydrology, water quality, and habitat structure. One of the primary concerns is the loss of wetland area. Encroachment for development, land conversion for agriculture, and the filling of wetlands for construction drastically reduce their extent. Such alteration of land cover disrupts the natural flow of water, impacts local microclimates, and diminishes the ability of wetlands to mitigate flooding by acting as natural sponges.

Water pollution poses another critical challenge. Urban and industrial runoff, as well as agricultural runoff containing fertilizers and pesticides, introduces harmful substances into wetland ecosystems. This pollution not only degrades water quality but also harms the flora and fauna that rely on these habitats. Moreover, the excessive nutrient load from runoff can trigger harmful algal blooms, disrupting the ecological balance and impacting aquatic life. The study by Ita (2018) demonstrated that human activities in proximity to wetlands have significantly contributed to the accumulation of toxic heavy metals within these ecosystems in Uyo Metropolis. The release of these metals was not without consequences for the resident flora species in these delicate environments. While certain species exhibited adaptability, those with lower tolerance levels experienced inhibited growth parameters. The levels of heavy metals in the soils exhibited remarkable variations across wetlands due to varying degrees of anthropogenic disturbances. Urban wetlands exhibited higher concentrations of Lead (Pb), Zinc (Zn), Iron (Fe), and Cadmium (Cd), whereas rural wetlands displayed elevated Nickel (Ni) levels. The interactions between heavy metals and plants unveiled both positive and negative relationships. In conclusion, the findings from this study revealed that the sources of heavy metal presence in wetlands were primarily attributed to human activities, and the presence of these metals beyond their tolerance levels had detrimental impacts on plant species. Therefore, it is recommended that appropriate monitoring initiatives be put in place around wetlands to prevent further contamination and deterioration of these ecosystems. Such measures are essential to ensure the sustained health and resilience of these invaluable habitats. Within the Itu Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, there exists no overseeing body to regulate the

utilization of wetlands. Consequently, the ongoing preservation of these wetlands relies solely on local residents who heavily exploit the available resources to meet their economic requirements. However, these unregulated activities have precipitated the degradation and even disappearance of wetland areas, highlighting the imperative for a structured approach to planning and overseeing wetland utilization. This study aims to evaluate the extent of degradation of wetlands in the Itu Local Government Area using remote sensing techniques, it will scrutinize the repercussions of such losses, and propose recommendations to ensure the enduring sustainability of wetlands within the study region.

2) Research Problem

The rapid decline of wetlands globally, exacerbated by various direct and indirect drivers, poses a significant ecological and societal challenge. Wetlands, which serve as critical transitional ecosystems between terrestrial and aquatic environments, are experiencing substantial losses, with a staggering 87 percent reduction over the last three centuries (Ramsar, 2014). This degradation threatens the well-being of 3.2 billion people worldwide and contributes to issues such as desertification, pollution, and species extinction. The problem of the research is hinged on the lack of insights on how wetlands in Itu LGA, Nigeria has evolved spatio-temporary, this knowledge gap needs to be filled in order to allow for informed decisions on the management of this eco-systemic resource. This research aims to assess the spatio-temporal status of wetlands in Itu for the last three decades. This study will also explore the ecological, economic, and societal repercussions of wetland degradation in the Itu Local Government Area and propose recommendations to ensure the sustainable management and utilization of wetlands in the study region. By addressing these issues, the research endeavours to contribute to a deeper understanding of the importance of wetlands, highlight the urgent need for effective regulatory measures, and provide insights into strategies for preserving and revitalizing wetland ecosystems in the face of global environmental challenges.

3) Philosophical Underpinning of the study

The philosophical foundation underpinning this study is rooted in environmental conservation ethics and sustainability principles. This research recognizes the intrinsic value of wetland ecosystems and aligns with the belief that nature possesses inherent worth beyond its utility to human beings (Kumar, 2018). This perspective draws inspiration from environmental philosophies such as deep ecology and biocentrism, which emphasize the moral obligation to protect and preserve the natural world for its own sake.

Central to this study is the concept of environmental stewardship, where humanity is regarded as caretakers of the Earth's resources, with a responsibility to safeguard the integrity of ecosystems and ensure their long-term viability (Swine, 2020). This perspective is closely linked to the anthropocentric viewpoint that human well-being is intricately connected to the health of the environment. Therefore, the study seeks to find a balance between human needs and the conservation of wetlands, recognizing that a healthy environment is essential for the prosperity and well-being of present and future generations.

Moreover, this research is guided by the principles of sustainability, which advocate for practices that meet the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. This perspective aligns with the Brundtland Commission's definition of sustainable development, which emphasizes the integration of economic, social, and environmental considerations. The study recognizes that the continued degradation of wetlands not only threatens biodiversity and ecological functions but also undermines the livelihoods and quality of life for communities that depend on these ecosystems. In essence, the study adopts a holistic approach that acknowledges the interconnectedness of ecological, economic, and societal factors. It recognizes the ethical imperative to protect and restore wetlands, not only for their utilitarian benefits but also as an ethical duty to maintain the Earth's ecological integrity. By delving into the challenges faced by wetlands in the Itu Local Government Area and proposing recommendations for their sustainable management, this research aligns with a broader philosophical commitment to environmental stewardship, ethics, and the long-term well-being of both natural systems and human societies

4) Study Area

The Itu Local Government Area is situated in the southeastern part of Nigeria and is designated as a Local Government Area within Akwa Ibom State. This administrative region encompasses an approximate land area of 606.10 square kilometers. Geographically, it lies between Latitude $5^{\circ}10'0''N$ and $7^{\circ}59'0''E$ east of the equator. The area is bordered to the North and North-East by Odukpani in Cross River State and Arochukwu in Abia State. To the West, it shares boundaries with Ibiono Ibom and Ikono Local Government Areas, while its southern and south eastern borders are marked by Uyo and Uruan Local Government Areas (Etim et al., 2023).

The Itu wetland, located within this region, lacks protective regulations. Situated within the Cross River and Akwa Ibom State basin, this area comprises diverse riverside forests and wetland grasslands that experience seasonal flooding (Ezealor, 2002). A notable characteristic is the presence of the swallow roost, situated in a low-lying depression near the confluence of the Cross River and its Eyong Creek tributary. This area is particularly vulnerable to flooding, with Asang hamlet, a densely populated settlement within Itu Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, being adversely affected (Ezealor, 2002).

The primary vegetation in this region is dominated by tall *Vossia cuspidate* grass. Additional elements include patches of *Mimosa pigra* thickets, as well as zones where *Echinochloa pyramidalis*, *E. stagnina*, *Ipeoma asarifolia*, *Nymphaea lotus*, and *Phragmites spp* are found. The vegetation in the seasonally flooded lowland forest swamps is characterized by a mixture of *Raphia* palms and broadleaved trees. The higher ground areas feature extensive stretches of *Elaeis guineensis* plantations and degraded secondary forests.

The region is home to a population of primates, including the rare *Cercopithecus nictitans* species, which inhabit the lowland forests. Notably, freshwater turtles and manatees, specifically *Trichechus senegalensis* (Vulnerable), also inhabit the area (Jacob et al., 2022).

Fig. 1. Map of Itu Local Government Area.

5) Research Methods

The research employed a combination of remote sensing and ground-truthing techniques to assess changes in land use patterns over a span of thirty years, specifically between the years 1992 and 2022. To achieve this, Landsat satellite imagery data for the two aforementioned epochs were obtained from the United States Geological Survey (USGS) website. These satellite images were crucial in discerning the prevailing status and extent of each land use category within the study area.

In the initial stages, pixels were strategically selected across the entire study area within the satellite images. Subsequently, ground-truthing activities were carried out to validate and corroborate the accuracy of the classifications made on the images. During ground-truthing, real-world observations were conducted on-site, and the findings were then compared against the land use classifications previously established on the images. This process served to ensure the reliability of the derived land use patterns.

The accuracy assessment was executed by randomly inspecting a significant number of pixels within the study area image. The outcomes of these random pixel checks were measured against the corresponding classified map to ascertain the degree of concurrence. By calculating the percentage of accurate pixels among the sampled ones, the research was able to estimate the overall accuracy of the entire land use map. This methodology provided a reasonable approximation of the precision and reliability of the land use classifications.

In addition to the satellite imagery data, the research also sourced supplementary information from various secondary data sources. These encompassed journal articles and government gazettes, which furnished additional context, insights, and supporting data to enrich the research's understanding of the study area, its historical context, and the factors influencing land use changes.

By integrating remote sensing data acquisition, ground-truthing validation, and utilization of secondary data sources, the research methodology ensured a comprehensive and robust approach to assessing the evolution of land use patterns within the study area over the specified time period.

6) Findings and Discussions

Table 1. Trend of Land Use Change in the Study Area, 1992 - 2022

	1992 (Km ²)	2022 (Km ²)	Magnitude	Percentage	Nature of Change
Water Body	37.882	35.275	- 2.607	0.696	Reduction
Wetlands (Swamps)	255.895	106.613	-149.282	39.877	Reduction
Fallowed Land	186.133	152.313	-36.820	9.836	Reduction
Cultivated Land	83.763	151.707	+67.944	18.149	Expansion
Built-up Area	42.427	160.132	+117.705	31.442	Expansion
Total	606.100	606.100	374.358	100.000	

Source: Extracted from LandSat Imageries 1992 and 2022 of Itu Local Government Area.

i) Water Body:

The "Water Body" category experienced a slight reduction in area, decreasing by 2.607 square kilometres or 0.696% of its original extent. This decrease could be attributed to factors such as land reclamation, sedimentation, or changes in hydrological patterns. The annual change rate for water bodies is 0.209%, indicating a relatively slow but consistent decrease in this land use type over the observed period.

ii) Wetlands (Swamps):

The most significant change is observed in "Wetlands (Swamps)" with a substantial reduction of 149.282 square kilometres or 39.877% of its area. This considerable decrease points to the extensive loss of wetland ecosystems within the study area, which can be due to drainage for agriculture, urban expansion, or other land-use changes. The annual change rate of 11.963% underscores the rapid decline of wetlands over the years, indicating a critical issue for environmental conservation. Such a significant reduction in wetland area highlights the severity of the issue. Wetlands play crucial roles in maintaining biodiversity, regulating water cycles, supporting wildlife habitats, and providing ecosystem services such as water purification and flood control.

iii) Fallowed Land:

The "Fallowed Land" category experienced a reduction in area, decreasing by 36.820 square kilometres or 9.836% of its original extent. This reduction could be attributed to the conversion of fallow land to other land uses, such as cultivation

or urban development. The annual change rate of 2.951% suggests a moderate decline in fallow land, indicating a shift in land utilization practices.

iv) Cultivated Land:

"Cultivated Land" witnessed a notable expansion, increasing by 67.944 square kilometres or 18.149% of its original extent. This growth reflects increased agricultural activities and potentially the conversion of other land use types to cultivation. The annual change rate of 5.445% indicates a steady growth in cultivated land, highlighting the importance of agriculture in the study area.

v) Built-up Area:

The most significant expansion is seen in "Built-up Area," which grew by 117.705 square kilometres or 31.442% of its original extent. This expansion signifies urbanization and the establishment of infrastructure, industries, and residences. The annual change rate of 9.432% demonstrates rapid urban growth and development, indicating increased human activities within the study area.

In conclusion, the analysis by each land use type reveals distinct trends and patterns of change. While cultivated land and built-up areas have expanded, wetlands and water bodies have faced substantial reductions. These changes point to significant shifts in land use practices, driven by factors such as urbanization, agriculture, and environmental alterations. The varying rates of change and magnitudes underscore the need for informed land management strategies to balance development with environmental conservation and sustainability.

Fig. 2. Land use/Land Cover Classified Imagery of the Study Area in 1992

Fig. 3. Land use/Land Cover Classified Images of the Study Area in 2022.

7) Environmental Implications Of Wetland Degradation In Itu Lga

The findings presented in the study, which highlight the reduction of wetlands in the Itu Local Government Area, carry significant environmental implications. These implications encompass a range of ecological, hydrological, and climatic

aspects, all of which have far-reaching effects on the environment and the well-being of both local communities and the broader ecosystem. Here, let's delve into the environmental implications of these findings:

- i) **Loss of Biodiversity:** The reduction in wetland resources directly translates to habitat loss for a diverse array of plant and animal species. Wetlands are vital breeding, nesting, and foraging grounds for numerous species, including those that are endangered or endemic. The loss of wetlands threatens the survival of these species, leading to disruptions in ecological balance and potential extinctions. This can cascade through the food chain, impacting the overall health and functioning of ecosystems.
- ii) **Disruption of Ecosystem Services:** Wetlands offer invaluable ecosystem services, such as water purification, flood regulation, and nutrient cycling. Diminishing wetland areas can disrupt these services, leading to decreased water quality, increased vulnerability to floods, and altered nutrient dynamics. This can have direct consequences on human health, infrastructure, and agricultural productivity, impacting the livelihoods of local communities.
- iii) **Hydrological Changes:** Wetlands play a crucial role in maintaining hydrological cycles by absorbing and slowly releasing water. Their reduction can alter local hydrological patterns, leading to increased surface runoff, reduced groundwater recharge, and changes in streamflow. Such changes can exacerbate flooding events, intensify erosion, and impact water availability for both human consumption and agricultural use.
- iv) **Loss of Carbon Sequestration:** Wetlands act as carbon sinks, sequestering carbon dioxide and other greenhouse gases from the atmosphere. The reduction of wetlands hinders their ability to capture and store carbon, contributing to increased greenhouse gas concentrations. This exacerbates the challenges of climate change by accelerating global warming and its associated effects.
- v) **Climate Change Feedbacks:** The loss of wetlands not only diminishes their carbon sequestration potential but also reduces their ability to regulate local climates. Wetlands help regulate temperature and humidity, and their decline can disrupt local weather patterns. This can have cascading effects on

regional ecosystems, agriculture, and water availability.

- vi) **Loss of Erosion Control:** Wetlands play a critical role in controlling erosion by stabilizing soil with their vegetation and water-retaining properties. Their reduction can lead to increased soil erosion, sedimentation in water bodies, and subsequent degradation of water quality. This can impact aquatic habitats and aquatic life, including fish populations.
- vii) **Cultural and Societal Impacts:** Beyond ecological implications, the loss of wetlands also has cultural and societal consequences. Wetlands often hold cultural and spiritual significance for local communities. The decline of wetlands can lead to the erosion of cultural heritage, disrupt traditional practices, and potentially impact the social cohesion of communities.

The findings regarding the degradation of wetlands in the Itu Local Government Area underscore a complex web of environmental implications. The decline of wetlands affects not only the ecosystems themselves but also reverberates through various environmental and societal aspects. Addressing these implications requires integrated and holistic approaches that prioritize wetland conservation, sustainable land use planning, and community engagement to ensure the long-term well-being of both the environment and its inhabitants.

8) Conclusion

In light of the comprehensive analysis conducted on the degradation of wetlands in the Itu Local Government Area, it is evident that this issue carries profound environmental, social, and economic implications. The research findings underscore the urgent need for informed and proactive measures to address the challenges posed by wetland degradation.

The study has revealed that wetlands, once vibrant and biodiverse ecosystems, have experienced significant losses over the past three decades. This loss extends beyond mere numerical figures; it represents a complex interplay of human activities, land use changes, and ecological shifts. The implications of these findings resonate across various dimensions of our world. From an environmental perspective, the decline in wetlands threatens biodiversity, disrupts ecosystem services, alters hydrological patterns, and contributes to carbon emissions. These changes have the potential to trigger a cascade of ecological consequences, impacting not only the natural world but also the livelihoods of communities dependent on the resources wetlands provide.

Moreover, the social fabric of communities is intricately woven with wetlands. These areas hold cultural significance, providing spaces for traditional practices, spiritual connections, and community cohesion. The loss of wetlands undermines cultural heritage and potentially erodes the social bonds that sustain communities. Economically, the reduction of wetlands affects livelihoods linked to fishing, agriculture, and tourism, which often depend on wetland ecosystems for sustenance and income. The decline of these sectors can lead to economic instability, particularly in areas where alternative opportunities

may be limited. The findings from this study underscore the interconnectedness of environmental, social, and economic factors, urging stakeholders to recognize the critical role wetlands play in the well-being of both nature and people. Addressing the diminishing status of wetlands requires a multi-faceted approach that integrates conservation efforts, sustainable land management practices, and community engagement.

To mitigate the negative consequences outlined in this research, it is imperative to implement robust regulatory frameworks that prioritize wetland protection, restoration, and sustainable use. Public awareness campaigns and community involvement are essential to garner support for conservation initiatives and promote responsible land use practices. The study serves as a call to action, highlighting the urgency of preserving wetlands not only for their intrinsic value but also for their vital contributions to our environment, culture, and society. By working together to safeguard these unique ecosystems, we can forge a path toward a more sustainable and harmonious future for both present and future generations.

References

- Abraham, S. (2004). Economic valuation of coastal wetlands: A study of Cochin backwaters in Kerala. <https://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/handle/10603/8970>.
- Dennis, K. and Andrew, M. (2015). The Effects of Wetland Degradation on the Socio Economic Welfare; A case study of Nabisasiro Wetland in Rubaga division.
- Efiong, J., Njoku, C., and Uzoezie, A. (2018). Wetland Encroachment in Calabar South Local Government Area, Cross River State. Paper Presented at the 59th Annual Conference of the Association of Nigerian Geographers at the Department of Geography, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria. (4th to 9th, November, 2018).
- Ekong, F. and Akpan, I. (2014). Characteristics and Methods of Wetlands Utilization in Ibiono Ibom LGA, Nigeria. *Management*, 4(14).
- Etim, N., Attah, A. and Okon, M. (2023). An Assessment of Land Use Change in Itu LGA, Nigeria: The Application of Relative Shannon Entropy. *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews* 4(7) pp 2911-2919.
- Ezealor, A. U. (2002). *Critical sites for biodiversity conservation in Nigeria*. Nigerian Conservation Foundation.
- Glasbergen, P. and Klijn, F., (1991). Integrated water and wetland management: towards a project approach, *Landscape and Urban Planning* 20 (1) 257-262,
- Gren, I. M., Folke, C., Turner, K., and Batemen, I. (1994). Primary and Secondary values of wetland ecosystems. *Environmental and Resource Economics*, 4(1), 55-74.
- Hemba, S., Elekwachi, W., Nwankwoala, H.O., Victoria, E., (2020). Ecosystem destruction and disaster risk incubation—A case of wetland loss and flood disasters in Makurdi Town of Nigeria. *Cent. Asian J. Environ. Sci. Technol. Innov.*, 1(4), 226-236.
- Idris, M. (2008). Damming Nigeria's Wetlands People: Communities work together to Restore Lives and Livelihoods. *World Rivers Review: Legacy Issue*.
- Kumar, S. (2015). Environmental Ethics: Issues and Solutions. *International Research Journal of Management Sociology and Humanity*. 6(7)338 -343.
- Ita, R. (2018) Effects of Heavy Metals on floristic attributes in human-influenced wetlands within Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *New York Science Journal* 11(10)
- Jacob, D. , Nelson, I. and Dickson (2022). Livelihood and Resource Interaction of Households in Itu Wetland, Nigeria. *American Journal of Environmental Sciences* 18 (5): 105.115 DOI: 10.3844/ajessp.2022.105.115.
- Nwankwoala, H. (2012). Case Studies on Coastal Wetlands and Water Resources in Nigeria. *European Journal of Sustainable Development* 1, 113-126
- Ogban, P. I., Effiong, G., Obi, J. and Ibia, T. (2011). Characteristics, potentials and constraints of wetland soils for Agricultural Development in Akwa Ibom State, South-eastern Nigeria. *Nig. J. Agric. Food Environ*, 7(2), 80-87.
- Ramsar (2005). Handbook for the Wise use of Wetlands. The Conceptual Framework. Retrieved on May 2, 2013at www.ramsar.org/key-guide-framework-wiseuse-e.htm. Paper 7.
- Swine, N. (2020). Issues in Environmental Ethics. *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research* 7(5) 698 -705.
- Tejuoso, o. Wetland uses/dynamics for agricultural purposes and its health implications in Lower Ogun River Basin, Lagos, Nigeria. A Technical Report Submitted to International Development Research Centre (IRDC), Nigeria.
- Verma, A. And Prakash, S.(2023). Wetland: An impact of Environmental Degradation and its Conservation. *Environment and Society* 1 pp 01-08.
- World Bank (2000). World Bank Report on Guidelines for Developing and Implementing National Wetland Policies.

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